

On Security Enhancement of the Internet of Things

Maha Alqallaf

Kuwait Ministry of Education, mahaag@moe.edu.kw

Abstract – In this paper, we look at the Internet of Things (IoT) and the serious security issues that surround it. We first analyze the overall layout of the IoT. This includes all layers such as the sensors, network, data processing and utilization. We also look at an alternate take on the typical network layout called edge computing. We then dive into the technical challenges of smart devices, more specifically, the security issues that they contain. We give an overview of some popular attacks that have taken advantage of these security issues. After showing the vulnerabilities of these unsecure devices, we examine what can be done to improve them. To start this off, we look at three common cryptography types in order to get a better understanding of them. This leads into an analysis of common encryption algorithms such as DES, AES, RSA, and ECC. Lastly, we discuss how these algorithms can be better implemented for the IoT, as well as how we can better enforce cyber security standards across all domains of the network.

I. Introduction

The IoT is a relatively new concept in our network environments. The emergence of new technology is starting to become a daily occurrence, it seems like everywhere you look, something is connected to the Internet. The most relatable example of this is the concept of a smart home. Everything from your thermostat, to your refrigerator, lights, and smoke detector can all communicate within the Internet without any interaction from a human after being properly set up.

These advancements within the IoT have made day-to-day life easier for most, as they are constantly connected to information. With these advancements come consequences. The growing number of devices within the internet of things causes the concern about security continues to rise. These concerns come with good cause.

Often, we hear about giant data hacks to large corporations that have sensitive information about millions of people. There are several security and privacy concerns across all layers of the IoT [1]. What happens if those same hackers start to target normal IoT users and devices? What kind of data can be accessed, and how vulnerable is it? What kind of measures are put into the creation of these devices in order to protect our data? These questions and more

will be looked at in detail throughout the entirety of this paper.

II. Internet of Things

The Internet of Things is the implementation of smart objects all around the world that connect to each other and the Internet in order to receive and utilize data from one another with minimum human interaction [1]. Whether it is your smart watch, sending health data to your phone, or your thermostat grabbing the outside temperature from the Internet, or even the lights in your house being controlled by your smart phone, they are all considered part of the internet of things. But how exactly do these things communicate?

A. How it Works

All devices that communicate within the internet of things contain sensors. Sensors are used to collect a variety of data, such as, GPS in a cell phone, heartbeat in a smartwatch, or a temperature gage in a thermostat. These sensors then send their information to a destination in the cloud in order to be processed.

In order for the data to be processed, the data must be transferred to a common area with all other data that is collected from other sensors within the network. When we think of IoT, we think of wireless, but there are multiple ‘wireless’ options that can be used to transfer and connect these devices. Such options include cellular networks, satellite, Wi-Fi, low-power wide-area networks (LPWAN) [2], and Bluetooth. Each of these options have their strengths and weaknesses, and the method the device uses really depends on the environment they are in. We will go over a few of the common ones here in summary.

Cellular networks are available almost everywhere these days. Most commonly, they are used for cell phones, because their range is relatively high. They can be used to track movement over long distances of things such as your smart watch while you are out on a run, or the location of your car [2].

Bluetooth is a very common communication transit for short ranges. It is used in homes pretty often to connect to such things as speakers, and common wearable smart items such as an activity tracker, smart watch, or wireless headphones. Usually, these connections are made to a smart phone, or some other kind of more powerful device.

Also commonly used in homes is Wi-Fi. Almost every home these days that have Internet access utilize Wi-Fi because of the ability to free roam while still having access, rather than being connected by an ethernet cord. Wi-Fi networks have one or more access points in which all devices go through in order to communicate with each other, and with the entirety of the Internet.

All the data that is being brought in from these sensors, over the possible networks discussed, then needs to be processed into useful information. The typical IoT structure has a centralized area to process all of the data collected. Keep in mind, all types of data are being recorded such as a picture, text, video, etc. In this method, data collected by the sensor is modified into machine code and then sent on to the centralized processing area in the cloud. The raw data is then input into the data processing mechanism, processed, and output into the desired human readable content [3].

Another way to do this is a process called edge computing. Edge computing brings data processing and storage closer to the sensor enabled devices that gather the data [4]. This idea would allow the edge

Fig. 1. Layout of the Internet of Things. This gives the path of how data moves and is manipulated throughout the network.

sensors to maximize their computational power for data gathering and add another layer of possible security to the environment [4]. It is also cheaper, and reduces the bandwidth needed to transfer the data or information.

After being processed, the desired information can be sent off to its destination, whether that would be another device, or to storage. Applications within other devices are then designed to handle the data being sent by specific devices on the network.

B. Technological Challenges

With the ever-expanding number of devices connecting to the IoT, certain challenges will be raised. The idea of a centralized node in the IoT will eventually have difficulties with the vast number of connections being made. Bottlenecking will become an issue if this continues to be the standard infrastructure. This is where the idea of the previously discussed edge computing could come in to play as the new standard. This would take a lot of the stress off of a central node since the processing is handled on the 'edge' closer to the sensing nodes in the area [4]. This would spread out the stress of processing to these edge devices rather than sending all of the processing tasks to the central area.

There are other proposed solutions to this problem, such as peer-to-peer communications [5]. This idea would completely cut out the idea of a centralized area to handle the traffic, as it would be passed and authenticated directly from endpoint to endpoint.

As numerous companies jump in to provide the latest and greatest IoT devices, compatibility becomes an issue. All companies have their own way of doing things, and therefore may not be compatible with other manufacturers' devices [5]. When you purchase devices, you often see a listing on the packaging of other manufacturers that the device is compatible with. This often leads to consumers sticking to one company for all of their IoT needs.

Lastly, and most importantly, security is a hot topic when it comes to the IoT. Along with your typical computers connected to the Internet, IoT devices are subject to security exploits as well. Often this is overlooked by consumers due to the 'set it and forget it' type of mentality that comes along with these types of devices. Simply put, the common user of many of these devices has no knowledge of the security concern that comes along with them.

All of the blame cannot fall on the consumer though. The manufacturers are the ones releasing these exploitable devices. In order to keep up with competitors, the production rate outweighs security therefore devices are released containing security exploits. Currently these exploits are typically

handled in later software patches. The problem with this is consumers often ignore mandatory updates or do not allow them to apply immediately, leaving their devices open to the countless vulnerabilities. New exploits are discovered frequently, so the devices continue to become more and more of a risk to the network they reside on. Attackers could use these vulnerabilities to gain access to the network and do whatever they please with the devices or sensitive information of the user. Let us look into a few examples of the vulnerabilities of the IoT being exploited.

C. Past Attacks

The Mirai botnet attack is one of the most infamous attacks as it was one of the first to use the IoT. This attack is known as a distributed denial-of-service attack (DDoS) which is laid out in Fig. 2. This attack was actually quite simple but was able to take down Dyn which is a Domain Name Server (DNS) provider for numerous big guns in the Internet community such as Twitter, Sound Cloud, and Reddit, all across the eastern United States [6].

Now, we say this attack was relatively simple because it did not use any particularly sophisticated techniques to compromise its target. The creator of this attack clearly knew of the unsecure nature of IoT devices and exploited them. The process contained two steps: (1) Scan the Internet for open Telnet ports. (2) Attempt to login to those devices with common known default username and password sets [6]. In all, Mirai had a list of 62 possible username/password combinations that it tried against every open telnet port that it came across [6]. This is known as a brute force dictionary attack.

When successful, the accessed device would then be loaded with malware from the initial control server or another bot. When hundreds of these devices are accessed, they become what is known as a botnet. Botnets can be used to carry out numerous tasks such as spamming, but in this case, it was used to carry out DDoS attacks. Essentially, a DDoS attack is used to disrupt the flow of normal Internet traffic by sending an abundant number of requests to a targeted IP address from all of the compromised devices on the botnet. This traffic overloads the targeted server leaving it unable to service any requests. DDoS attacks can be used across multiple OSI layers, but Mirai was created mostly to carry out HTTP floods [6].

As described earlier, IoT devices were an easy target for this attack. Countless users use the default passwords on their devices and do not think twice about changing them, as many of these devices sit on your network and do not require much human interaction. Those devices are easy long-term

Fig. 2. Botnet DDoS Attack. This is a simple overview of how a DDoS attack is carried out using infected IoT devices that have become part of a botnet.

members of botnets as their exploitation will not normally be noticed by the regular user.

Not all botnet attacks are this simple. Another example of an IoT botnet is one known as Reaper. Reaper is thought to be derived from the previously discussed Mirai, but the way it gains access to devices is quite different. Reaper uses known hardware vulnerabilities within IoT devices such as routers, DVRs, or wireless cameras [7].

One example of these vulnerabilities can be described by CVE-2017-8225 [8], which states that P2P enabled WIFICAM devices incorrectly check the credentials of .ini files. The attacker easily bypasses this by providing empty login credentials and gains access into the system and opens a backdoor for future access. Now there are numerous other exploits with varying complexity that Reaper uses to gain access. In fact, a number of the exploits have been solved by either patches or updated model releases. The problem lies in those unpatched and older devices that will continue to be vulnerable and used by reaper and other botnet malware.

In addition to this botnet problem, all information on your network is also at risk. The exploits previously can be used for more than just creating botnets. Once they have access to a device on your network, it opens up the possibility to other attacks as well, such as ransomware.

Ransomware has been a common attack to consumers for the last several years, most commonly, in targeted emails designed to trick the user into opening malware. The user opens a normal looking attachment within the email and that immediately

infects the computer and encrypts all of its files. In some cases this can spread to multiple systems on the network.

When it comes to attacking the IoT devices, ransomware works a little differently. Similar to the previously described botnet attacks, ransomware motivated attackers could gain access to your devices through certain bugs or exploits that have not been properly patched.

For example, this was demonstrated a few years back at IoT village by Andrew Tierney of Pen Test Partners [9]. Specifically, he did this to an IoT enabled thermostat. Within the thermostat's connection application, he was able to remotely find a function blatantly called `firmware` and analyze the code with a tool to locate the file system. After getting there, he found the whole system is run by one binary as root. He was then able to analyze that code and find a way to possibly get access as root. With a bit of brute force through a technique using ping, Tierney was able to find that the images in the executable were exploitable when loading settings [9].

Once he had access as root it was easy for Tierney to lock up the device. He simply created a screensaver noting the hack, and setting a screen lock that changed PINs every 30 seconds. This would make it nearly impossible for the consumer to ever gain access without paying the ransom to the hacker.

As we can see, this was much too easy for the hacker to get access and change the code. Tierney goes on to explain what could have been done to prevent this exploit. He notes that the firmware he accessed should be encrypted in a properly secured system. If it were encrypted, it would be nearly impossible for him to gain access and analyze the code. In addition, the code should have some sort of checksum against it that would know if it had been modified and not accept the modifications.

In this section, we described just two possible ways the Internet of Things can be exploited for devious reasons by hackers. There are numerous other things that hackers can use the unsecure devices for such as spreading malware across your entire network, or accessing sensitive personal information from your network. All of these reasons strongly support the need for better security measures on IoT devices.

III. IoT Security

We just went over a couple of examples of how easily IoT devices can be taken advantage of for devious operations. Now we will take a closer look at the current security measures in place, any standards they follow, and what could possibly be done to improve the security of these devices.

Now when looking into security there are obviously different layers that need to be protected. You have your application layer, the network layer, and then the device hardware itself. The previously described botnet attack would be a network layer attack. First let us look at what an edge computing solution could do in order to prevent this, and other similar security concerns.

A. Edge Computing Solution

In the initial overview of IoT architecture, we mentioned the idea of edge computing, which has the ability to take tasks away from the resource starved IoT devices and the cloud. The Cloud has the resources to handle security, but it is simply too far away from the end devices. A solution to this would be an addition of edge computing devices that are closer to the smart devices. These edge devices would have a higher amount of resources allowing it to handle numerous tasks better than an IoT enabled device doesn't have the necessary resources for, as it would take away from their main task of gathering information.

One of these tasks the edge computing can handle is security. The idea for an edge security design can be broken into three parts: user-centric, device-centric, and end-to-end security [4]. With these three implementations, security concerns at all layers could be handled.

User-centric security within the edge addresses the concern of uninformed users using untrusted devices to connect to the IoT network. The idea here would be to design a trusted domain using edge computing [4]. Once designed, the trusted domain can control the secure access to everything across the IoT network it is implemented on. Using edge devices, this security measure would handle user access verification, as well as security policies for those verified users such as the utilization of antivirus and firewalls [4].

Device-centric IoT security addresses the security concerns of each individual device on the network. The idea here is for the edge device to take over all security functions from the IoT device [4]. One proposed solution called EdgeSec gives the idea to handle device security profiles, security analysis, protocol mapping, security simulation, communication management, and request handling all with modules within the edge device [4]. With these capabilities the edge could handle device profiles that know its specific security requirements and implement them for each device.

Lastly, end-to-end security would include the handling of encryption and authentication across the entirety of the connection. In this scenario, the edge layer acts as a bridge between the IoT device and the

cloud [4]. Within the edge device, data could be properly secured and utilize more extraneous encryption algorithms that the IoT device cannot handle. This would better ensure the security of that data as it is then passed onto the cloud.

Edge computing also opens up the possibility of adding a firewall closer to the IoT devices [4]. Here all traffic from the IoT device into the edge device would be examined and tested against security policies that have been set. This would greatly decrease the possibility of unwanted traffic coming from the device such as an attempted DDoS. For example, there could be a policy set in place for a ceiling on the amount of traffic coming from the device at one time. If there is a large amount of traffic coming from the device, it could then be denied by the firewall to prevent a DDoS attack if they security ever came to that.

When comparing this edge-based architecture with our typical IoT layout today, as the number of smart devices available continues to expand, it is obvious to me that this is the way the future should be trending. The problem with edge computing is that it has not been successfully implemented with the IoT yet, but a lot of research is still going into it. A few hurdles that still need to be crossed include lightweight protocols between the edge layer and smart devices and security of the edge layer. Since this solution cannot yet be implemented, we would like to take a look at what could possibly be done now in order to enhance the security of current IoT networks.

B. Botnet Prevention

If you recall, the Mirai botnet attack used a brute force dictionary attack in order to gain access to IoT devices. So obviously the first measure of defense would be to change default passwords immediately. They should be changed before ever being added to a network. This could also be prevented by the manufacturer itself. If the manufacturer generated randomized passwords for each device, and then provided that to the user in packaging, this would at least increase the difficulty of easy dictionary attacks. It should be stated that not all botnet attacks are going to be dictionary attacks, so, in addition, it helps to make sure your device software is up to date with patches. This will minimize the number of exploits that can be used to access the device.

In addition to security measures that require human interaction, the device, network, and application should all have other measures in place, such as the ones discussed with edge computing, to ensure a high level of security against their data and infrastructure.

C. Cryptography and Encryption

Encryption was briefly mentioned earlier when we went over Tierney's exploitation of a smart thermostat device. Encryption can be used in any of our targeted network layers in order to harden the security of sensitive information even if a hacker is able to gain access to the system. It can also be used to encrypt data traveling across the network layer. Let us take a look at a few encryption standards that are used today by IoT devices.

To really understand encryption, you need to understand cryptography as well. Essentially, cryptography is the art of writing plain text into unreadable text. There are basically three categories of cryptography, which are secret key cryptography, public key cryptography, and hash functions.

Secret key methods use a single key for both encryption and decryption. This means that the key used must be known and distributed between the sender and the receiver. Within the secret key category there are two sub types: stream ciphers and block ciphers [10]. Stream ciphers encrypt one bit at a time and constantly change the key. This can be executed in a few ways. Since it is done one bit at a time, the encryption and decryption functions can synchronize and constantly change their function bit by bit [10]. On the other hand, the same function could be used on the entire message being sent and be modified after the entirety of that is sent.

Block ciphers are a little more complicated. With block ciphers, a block of data is encrypted one at a time using the same key on each block [10]. The big difference between block ciphers and stream ciphers is that a block cipher using the same key, will encrypt a plaintext block into the exact same cipher text block, and when using stream cipher, the cipher text will always be different, although it should be noted that repetition is possible eventually [10]. Since secret key cryptography is mostly used for confidentiality and privacy, this is commonly used within an IoT network.

Next, we have public key cryptography. The simple difference between public and secret key cryptography is that in public key, two keys are used, one for encryption and one for decryption. Those two keys are deemed the public key and the private key [10]. The two keys use similar one-way mathematical functions in order to encrypt. The public key is used to encrypt, while the private key is used to decrypt. This type of cryptography is mostly used for authentication.

Lastly, hash functions do not utilize any keys. They are considered 'one-way' encryption and therefore cannot be decrypted to the original plain text [10]. This kind of cryptography is commonly used to test the integrity of a file, and for password encryption.

Now that we have the essentials of cryptography noted, it will be easier to understand how encryption works as cryptography really sets the tone for how any

encryption method is utilized. Here we will look at three encryption methods. Those being the Data Encryption Standard, the U.S Government Advanced Encryption and RSA.

The Data Encryption Standard (DES) and the U.S Government Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) are two standards provided by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). DES is quite outdated but it was the initial building block for future encryptions such as AES so it is worth going over.

DES is an example of the previously discussed secret key cryptography. Specifically, it is a 64-bit block cipher. This means a 64-bit block of plain text is encrypted into exactly a ciphered 64-bit block of text. When using DES, the same method is used to encrypt and decrypt the information. This is known as a symmetric algorithm. DES uses the following steps [11]:

1. Accepts an input of 64 – bit plaintext and 56-bitkey with 8 bits of parity.
2. The bits within the plaintext block are shifted around.
3. The 8 parity bits are removed from the key and the remaining 56 bits are split into two halves of 28.
4. The two halves are shifted by one or two bits depending on which round number it is going through and then recombined.
5. After the combination, the key block is compressed to 48 bits from the original 56.
6. Now the 64 bit plaintext block is split into two 32-bit blocks.
7. One of those 32-bit blocks goes through expansion permutation to increase its size to 48 bits. This matches its size with the key block created in step 5.
8. The output from step 7 is OR'd with the key result from step 5.
9. The step 8 result then goes through substitution and reduction to get back down to 32-bits. Those 32 – bits go through permutation again, and are OR'd with the other half of plaintext that has been untouched from step 6.
10. The two halves are swapped and go back through this process again.

As mentioned before, AES is an improvement on DES that is still used today. AES is also a block cipher but it accepts 128-bit data blocks. The key can be 128, 192, or 256 bits [13]. The length of the key determines how many rounds of processing it will go through. 128-bit keys mean there will be 10 rounds of processing, 12 rounds of processing for 192-bit keys, and 14 rounds for 256-bit keys. Each of those rounds have multiple steps, which include single-byte based substitution, row rearranging, column mixing, and

addition of the round key. Here are the steps for a

Fig. 3. AES encryption and decryption steps laid out in order to give a better visual of how these steps are carried out.

process using a 128-bit key [11]:

1. Initialize the state array and add the initial round key to the state array.
2. Do what is known as a ‘usual’ round 9 times. This includes:
 - a. Sub bytes: This substitute one byte of two hexadecimal digits.
 - b. Shift rows: The rows within the 128-bit block are shifted.
 - c. Mix Columns: The columns are then mixed similar to the rows.
 - d. Lastly, a Round key is added using matrix addition.
3. On the final round (round 10):
 - a. Sub bytes
 - b. Shift Rows
 - c. Add Round Key (10)
4. The cipher text is output.

In order to decrypt AES encrypted text, inverse functions are needed for each step described above. The decryption would go through the same number of rounds using inverse functions of sub bytes, shift rows, add key round and mix columns [11] A full layout of these steps can be seen in Fig. 3.

When comparing AES and DES, the differences are pretty clear. DES always alters just half of the block each step making it less efficient and less effective. Secondly, the key size of AES is twice the size of DES

even at its smallest. If you recall AES key size can be 128, 192, or 256 while DES uses 64. Simply put, a larger key size makes it much more secure. The algorithm used by AES is also more efficient which allows it be used in smaller devices with less processing power, such as the smaller IoT devices.

The most common algorithm using public key cryptography in the IoT world today is known as RSA. It was created in the 1970s and is the foundation for future public key encryption. Commonly it is used to confirm correct access of data by the correct receiver. How RSA works [11]:

1. Generate two prime numbers (p and q)
2. Compute $n = pq$ and $x = (p-1)(q-1)$
3. Generate e where $1 < e < x$ and e is relatively prime to x.
4. Compute the unique integer d, where $1 < d < x$ and $e * d$ is equivalent to x.
5. The above steps will give you the public key (n, e) and the private key (d).
6. The message is encrypted using the public key with the equation $c = m^e \text{ mod } n$ where m = plain text and c = cipher text.
7. Upon proper reception the message can be decrypted using the private key using $m = c^d \text{ mod } n$

Another public key cryptography is Elliptical Curve Cryptography (ECC), which can be used in the same ways RSA can be use, such as protecting data between sender and receiver and verifying secure connections. The biggest advantage with ECC is that it takes way less resources to create the same amount of security in a key. For example, a 164-bit key in ECC is equivalent to a 1024 bit key in RSA [12]. ECC is a quite fascinating but is pretty difficult to understand. Here are the basics of the algorithm [12]:

1. An elliptical curve is generated using $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$.
2. Generate Keys:
 - a. Select a random number (d) between 1 and prime n - 1.
 - b. Sender generate the public key using $QA = dA * P$ where Q is the public key, and P is a point on the curve.
 - c. Receiver generates a public key using a different number, but the same point $QB = dB * P$.
 - d. dA and dB becomes the private keys for the sender and receiver respectively.
3. Generate Signature
 - a. $e = \text{HASH}(m)$ where m is the original message
 - b. Sender selects a random integer k in range [1, n-1]
 - c. The signature (r,s) is generated as $r = x1 \text{ mod } n$ and $s = k^{-1}(e + dA * r)$ where $(x1, y1) = k * P$ and n = Order of G.

4. Encryption

- a. m is represented on the elliptical curve as point M.
- b. Sender selects random number k is selected in the range [1, n-1]
- c. Two points (B1, B2) represent the cipher text generated.
- d. $B1 = k * P, B2 = M + (k * P)$

5. Decryption

- a. The original data M is decrypted by the receiver using $M = B2 - (dB * B1)$.

6. Verify Signature

- a. Receiver verifies the signature (r,s) is in the range of [1, n-1].
- b. Calculate the hash function used in signature generation.
- c. $w = s^{-1} \text{ mod } n$
- d. $u1 = e * w \text{ mod } n$
- e. $u2 = r * w \text{ mod } n$
- f. $(x1, y1) = u1 * P + u2 * dA$
- g. If $x1 = r \text{ mod } n$ then the signature is valid.

When comparing RSA and ECC encryption algorithms, they are fairly different. Overall ECC is better in most categories. RSA is simpler to understand, but the complexity of ECC really just makes it even more secure. The biggest benefit of ECC, as mentioned previously, is the ability to create the same level of security with smaller keys [12]. The fact that keys are smaller, makes their generation quicker, and therefore more efficient than RSA which has a relatively slow key generation process. In addition, ECC signatures are computed in two stages which is more secure than RSA where signatures are difficult to implement securely [12].

IV. Possible Enhancements and Solutions

When addressing the problem of IoT security, clearly there are options available in order to raise the level of security provided by the device and network. We have just gone over a few of those options when it comes to encryptions and better practice by the manufacturer. The problem is there are no rules or requirements set in place that the manufacturers have to follow. There can also be better utilization of encryption so it can better be implemented in IoT devices.

A. Rules, Regulations, and Visibility

The first step in security is having the available tools in order to implement them. Clearly that is in place as encryption methods are available and IoT server hosts such as Google or Amazon Web Services (AWS) use the strongest security they can when you use their devices. The problem then becomes ensuring all

devices are using the tools available to them to make them as secure as possible.

One solution would be to put security rules in place that manufacturers must follow in order to release their product to the market. There are already guidelines provided by third parties such as the Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP). These kinds of documents provide guidance across the entirety of the process of creating the IoT. This could include guidance for the manufacturer, consumer, network provider, and application developers. A document similar to this would lay great ground work for manufacturers and developers to follow.

It may be impossible to force all IoT device providers to follow a guideline as implementing security takes time and money, causing prices of devices to go up, making them less appealing to the customer. A better practice may be to offer some sort of notice on secure device packaging. For example, if a device implements a certain security guideline and passes a rigorous security test, then there could be a seal of security 'certified' on their packaging letting the consumer know that this device is safe to use on a network with less security concerns. The secure devices may be more expensive, but at least they would have the visibility to let the consumer know that the device is less of a security concern to their home network when compared to the lower priced, untested devices.

B. Encryption Improvements for the IoT

As discussed, there are already encryption algorithms provided and implemented in some devices in the IoT. With that said, there have been proposed enhancements to better utilize these encryption methods within an IoT network. Encryption methods used in these devices and networks need to be as efficient as possible to utilize minimal processing power in order to maximize performance and limit delay for the consumer. Here are a couple proposed encryption enhancements.

First, proposed by Vijayalakshmi and Arockiam in 2017, is the idea of multilevel encryption [13]. This method is proposed in order to secure the data collected by sensors as it is passed to the server, while encryption happens in the gateway. This technique uses the Merkle Hellman Knapsack Cryptosystem along with the previously discussed ECC. The way this implementation would work is first, the plain text would be parted by each character and converted to binary values [13]. Those values are then encrypted using Merkle Hellman encryption. This creates a subset problem that can be solved fluently [13]. Through modular representation and permutation, the increasing nature can be hidden [13]. The encrypted

bits are then input into the ECC encryption method. ECC then creates a cipher text from the provided encryption.

This proposed process adds a second layer of security to an already secure process in ECC. It is also claimed that this process improves overall computation time which is essential in minimizing delay times for the consumer [13].

Another proposed enhancement to IoT encryption was proposed by Bhandari and Kirubanand relatively recently in 2018 [14]. They propose what they call an enhanced encryption technique, and their main goal is to transfer data effectively and efficiently from one end to another securely, while maintaining confidentiality, integrity, and authentication [14]. This idea uses three different encryption algorithms including the previously discussed ECC and AES along with Elliptical Curve Diffie Hellman (ECDH). This is an interesting proposition as it utilizes both symmetric and asymmetric algorithms [16]. In reference to our previous discussion about cryptography, this means it utilizes both secret key and public key cryptography.

This process starts by both the sender and receiver generating key pairs using ECC [14]. Both then register themselves with a public key server by passing their newly generated public keys and MAC addresses. After successful registration, the sender and receiver then pass their keys and MAC addresses to each other. The receiver then queries the public key server with the MAC address sent by the sender. The server should then return the public key of the sender and therefore verify the received key. The sender also does the above verification with the public key server. After successful verification, the sender and receiver agree on a common secret key using the two public keys and generate using ECDH. Lastly, they open up communication and use AES for encrypting and decrypting their communications [14].

We believe that the enhanced encryption technique to be a unique take on the future implementation of encryption. The idea of using a combination of encryption algorithms along with different steps of the authentication process is a great start at making sure no data is exploited. ECC and AES are also both low energy type of algorithms, so it would be possible to utilize both of them within IoT devices.

V. Conclusion

The IoT is currently a very insecure mechanism. As it continues to expand, so will the security concerns. Much of this has to do with the computing power of smart device along with the distance between that device and the central server in the cloud.

In the near future, it would be expected that we can start securely implementing edge-based solutions for IoT devices. This would be the greatest solution to the security problems we have discussed. In the meantime, we have described the possible solutions we can carry out in order to fill the gap in security concerns that we have today. To fill that gap, effort will be needed from anyone associated with the IoT.

In addition, the encryption mechanisms we laid out are available for use today, and some of them such as ECC and AES are considered lightweight and can be used on low resource devices, such as many across the IoT, including lightbulbs, thermostats and switches. There have even been improvements provided in [13, 14] that include the combination of multiple algorithms in order to enhance security. With the implementation of these improvements, and better security regulations for manufacturers, we can make the IoT world a more secure place.

VI. References

- [1] J. Sathish Kumar and D. R. Patel, "A Survey on Internet of Things: Security and Privacy Issues," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 90, no. 11, pp. 20–26, 2016
- [2] A. Junnila, "How IoT Works – Part 2: Connectivity," *Trackinno*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://trackinno.com/2018/06/04/how-iot-works-part-2-connectivity/>. [Accessed: 18- Nov- 2019].
- [3] A. Junnila, "How IoT Works – Part 3: Data Processing," *Trackinno*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://trackinno.com/2018/07/06/how-iot-works-part-3-data-processing/>. [Accessed: 18- Nov- 2019].
- [4] K. Sha, T. Yang, W. Wei and S. Davari, "A survey of edge computing based designs for IoT security," *Digital Communications and Networks*, 2019. Available: 10.1016/j.dcan.2019.08.006 [Accessed 20 November 2019].
- [5] A. Banafa, "Three Major Challenges Facing IoT - IEEE Internet of Things," *iot.ieee.org*, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://iot.ieee.org/newsletter/march-2017/three-major-challenges-facing-iot.html>. [Accessed: 20- Nov- 2019].
- [6] M. Antonakakis et al., "Understanding the Mirai Botnet," in 26th USENIX Security Symposium, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2017, pp. 1093 - 1110.
- [7] B. Krebs, "Reaper: Calm Before the IoT Security Storm?" *Krebsonsecurity.com*, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://krebsonsecurity.com/2017/10/reaper-calm-before-the-iot-security-storm/>. [Accessed: 23- Nov- 2019].
- [8] "NVD - CVE-2017-8225," *Nvd.nist.gov*, 2019. Available: <https://nvd.nist.gov/vuln/detail/CVE-2017-8225>. [Accessed: 25- Nov- 2019].
- [9] "Thermostat Ransomware: a lesson in IoT security | Pen Test Partners," *Pentestpartners.com*, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pentestpartners.com/security-blog/thermostat-ransomware-a-lesson-in-iot-security/>. [Accessed: 25- Nov- 2019].
- [10] G. Kessler, "An Overview of Cryptography," *Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University Scholarly Columns*, 2016. [Accessed 27 November 2019].
- [11] P. Mahajan and A. Sachdeva, "A Study of Encryption Algorithms AES, DES and RSA for Security," *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology Network, Web & Security*, vol. 13, no. 15, 2013. [Accessed 25 November 2019].
- [12] A. Zargar, M. Manzoor and T. Mukhtar, "Encryption/decryption using elliptical curve cryptography," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 48-51, 2017.
- [13] A. Vijayalakshmi, "Enhancing the security of IoT data using multilevel encryption," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 841-845, 2017.
- [14] R. Bhandari and V. Kirubanand, "Enhanced encryption technique for secure IoT data transmission," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3732-3738, 2019.